

Detection of *Hedyotis corymbosa* (L.) Lam. in traditional Chinese medicine *Hedyotis diffusa* Willd. with the Proofman-LMTIA method

Yongzhen Wang^{1*}, Juan Tian^{1*}, Dan Zhou^{1,2*}, Deguo Wang¹, Bailing Yin³

¹ Key Laboratory of Biomarker Based Rapid-detection Technology for Food Safety of Henan Province, Food and Pharmacy College, Xuchang University, Xuchang 461000, China

² Xuchang University, Xuchang 461000, China

³ Yuzhou Houshengtang Traditional Chinese Medicine Co., Ltd, Xuchang 452570, China

Corresponding author: Deguo Wang (wangdg666@126.com)

Received 3 May 2025 ♦ Accepted 20 June 2025 ♦ Published 25 July 2025

Citation: Wang Y, Tian J, Zhou D, Wang D, Yin B (2025) Detection of *Hedyotis corymbosa* (L.) Lam. in traditional Chinese medicine *Hedyotis diffusa* Willd. with the Proofman-LMTIA method. Pharmacia 72: 1–9. <https://doi.org/10.3897/pharmacia.72.e157723>

Abstract

There is increasing demand for the traditional Chinese medicine *Hedyotis diffusa* Willd. due to its effectiveness in treating hepatitis and malignant tumors of the liver, lung, and stomach. *Hedyotis corymbosa* (L.) Lam. has commonly become an adulterant of *H. diffusa* Willd. The proofreading enzyme-mediated probe cleavage coupled with ladder-shape melting temperature isothermal amplification (Proofman-LMTIA) can specifically and sensitively detect nucleic acids. In this study, the Proofman-LMTIA method was established to identify *H. corymbosa* (L.) Lam. for quality control of the traditional Chinese medicine *Hedyotis diffusa* Willd. The LMTIA primers and Proofman probe were designed using the internal transcribed spacer 2 (ITS2) of *H. corymbosa* (L.) Lam. as the target. The reaction temperature was optimized, and the specificity and sensitivity were determined. The repeatability and reliability were also assessed. The optimal reaction temperature of the Proofman-LMTIA method was 61 °C. The method demonstrated high specificity, repeatability, reliability, and sensitivity, with amplification completed within 20 min and a detection limit of 10 pg/μL genomic *H. corymbosa* (L.) Lam. This study successfully established a Proofman-LMTIA method for the detection of *H. corymbosa* (L.) Lam., providing an effective approach to distinguish authentic from adulterated traditional Chinese medicine.

Keywords

fake medicine, *Hedyotis diffusa* Willd., *Hedyotis corymbosa* (L.) Lam., Proofman-LMTIA

Introduction

Hedyotis diffusa Willd. is a well-known traditional Chinese medicine due to its antitumor, immunomodulatory, antimutagenic, anti-inflammatory, hepatoprotective, antioxidative, and neuroprotective activities. It is widely used for the effective

treatment of hepatitis, tonsillitis, sore throat, appendicitis, urethral infection, and malignant tumors of the liver, lung, and stomach (Liang et al. 2008; Zou et al. 2021; Huang et al. 2022; Zhang et al. 2022). With the increasing clinical demand for *H. diffusa* Willd., many inauthentic (counterfeit or adulterated) species have appeared on the market, among

* Contributed equally to this work.

which the most common adulterant is *Hedyotis corymbosa* (L.) Lam. (Li et al. 2010; Yu et al. 2012). Therefore, it is important to detect *H. corymbosa* (L.) Lam. to ensure quality control of herbal materials and preparations.

Many techniques have been used to detect inauthentic traditional Chinese herbs, such as loop-mediated isothermal amplification (LAMP) assay (Rodrigues et al. 2024), droplet digital PCR (ddPCR) or MGB probe-based multiplex ddPCR (Xu et al. 2022; Xu et al. 2025), DNA metabarcoding (shotgun metagenomic sequencing or DNA barcoding) (Bansala et al. 2018; Raclariu et al. 2018; Xin et al. 2018; Noh et al. 2021), HPTLC (Raclariu et al. 2018), infrared spectroscopy or near-infrared spectroscopy (An et al. 2024; Luo et al. 2024), quadrupole time-of-flight mass spectrometry (UPLC-QTOF/MS) (Jin et al. 2024), and thin-layer chromatography-image analysis (An et al. 2024). However, increasing attention has been paid to the ladder-shape melting temperature isothermal amplification (LMTIA) technique for the identification of authentic and inauthentic Chinese medicinal herbs, as it is fast, sensitive, and specific and does not require expensive equipment (Wang et al. 2021).

The LMTIA technique has been applied for the rapid discrimination of *Panax quinquefolium* and *Panax ginseng* (Zhang et al. 2023), detection of *Bupleurum scorzonerifolium* Willd. and *Bupleurum chinense* DC (Liu et al. 2024), and rapid identification of *Radix Achyranthis Bidentatae* and *Radix Cyathulae* (Cui et al. 2024a). However, no report has yet been published on the detection of *H. corymbosa* (L.) Lam. using the LMTIA technique.

Therefore, this study proposes and establishes the Proofman-LMTIA method for the accurate detection of *H. corymbosa* (L.) Lam. in the herbal materials and preparations of *H. diffusa* Willd.

Materials and methods

LMTIA primer and probe design

The multi-copy internal transcribed spacer (ITS) sequence is widely used for genus and species identification (Xiao et al. 2024). The ITS2 region of *Hedyotis corymbosa* (GenBank sequence ID: AY854053.1) was used as the target for designing the LMTIA primers and probe. The sequence was analyzed using Oligo7 software (Molecular Biology Insights, Inc., Colorado Springs, CO, USA) to select fragments exhibiting a ladder-shaped melting temperature curve and a GC content of 40%–80% (Cui et al. 2024b). The target sequence was aligned with the corresponding sequences of *H. diffusa*, *H. pinifolia*, and *H. tenelliflora* using DNAMAN software. The LMTIA primers and probe were designed using the online software Primer3Plus (<http://www.primer3plus.com/>), and the Proofman probe was designed based on the loop primer (LF or LB) sequence. The probe was labeled with a fluorophore and a quencher at the 3' end mismatch nucleotide and 5' end nucleotide, respectively (Yao et al. 2025).

DNA preparation

Dried whole herb samples of *H. corymbosa*, *H. diffusa*, *H. pinifolia*, and *H. tenelliflora* were provided by Yuzhou Houshengtang Traditional Chinese Medicine Co., Ltd. (Xuchang, Henan Province, China). The samples were ground using an SL-100 high-speed multifunctional grinder (Songqing Hardware Factory, Yongkang, Zhejiang Province, China). Genomic DNA (gDNA) was extracted using the Plant Genomic DNA Nucleic Acid Extraction Kit in conjunction with the NP968-C Automatic Nucleic Acid Extractor (Xian Tianlong Technology Co., Ltd, Xi'an, Shanxi Province, China) (Yao et al. 2025). The ITS1, 5.8S rRNA gene, and ITS2 regions of the gDNAs were sequenced to verify the authenticity of the samples.

Temperature optimization and specificity determination

The Proofman-LMTIA reaction system for temperature optimization and specificity determination consisted of 0.16 μL (100 μM) each of primers F and B, 0.04 μL (100 μM) each of primers LF and LB, 0.1 μL (10 μM) of probe, 2 μL of 5 \times premix dNTP buffer, 0.4 μL (100 U/ μL) of Bst DNA polymerase (Merit Biotech [Shandong] Co., Ltd., Heze, Shandong Province, China), and 1 μL of genomic DNA (gDNA) template, blank control, or negative control. The total reaction volume was adjusted to 10 μL with DEPC-treated water (ddH₂O) (Cui et al., 2024a). All isothermal amplification experiments were performed using a Gentier 96E Medical PCR Analyzer System (Xian Tianlong Technology Co., Ltd., Xi'an, Shanxi Province, China), and fluorescence signals were recorded every 30 s for a total of 40 cycles (Zhang et al. 2023; Liu et al. 2024).

Sensitivity determination of the Proofman-LMTIA method

The gDNAs of *H. corymbosa* were diluted to final concentrations of 1 ng/ μL , 100 pg/ μL , and 10 pg/ μL . According to the above reaction system, mixtures containing 1 μL of *H. corymbosa* gDNA at each concentration were amplified under the optimized temperature conditions. ddH₂O was used as the negative control (Cui et al. 2024a).

Repeatability and reliability assessment of the Proofman-LMTIA method

The repeatability and reliability of *H. corymbosa* detection were assessed using the Proofman-LMTIA reaction system. Eight *H. corymbosa* gDNA samples were used as positive controls, and eight ddH₂O samples were used as negative controls (Liu et al. 2024). The Proofman-LMTIA reactions were carried out at the optimized temperature, with fluorescence signals collected every 30 s for a total of 40 cycles. The resulting isothermal amplification curves were analyzed and evaluated to determine consistency and reproducibility.

Commercial sample test

Eight commercial samples of the traditional Chinese medicine *H. diffusa* were purchased from the online platform Taobao to detect adulteration with *H. corymbosa* using the established Proofman-LMTIA method. The gDNA of the eight samples was extracted using the kit described in the DNA preparation section. According to the established LMTIA reaction system, each reaction mixture included 1 μ L (1 ng/ μ L) of DNA template from the commercial samples and was run at the optimized temperature. The gDNA of *H. corymbosa* served as the positive control, and ddH₂O served as the negative control.

For comparison, the eight dried whole herb samples were also analyzed using third-generation sequencing. Sequencing followed the protocol of the Native Barcoding Kit SQK-NBD114.24 (Shanghai Baichuangyi Biotechnology Co., Ltd., Shanghai, China), with steps summarized as follows: DNA extraction; PCR amplification (forward primer: ATGCGATACTTGGTGTGAAT; reverse primer: GACGCTTCTCCAGACTACAATT; reaction conditions: 30 cycles of 98 °C for 5 s, 54 °C for 10 s, and 72 °C for 5 s); library preparation (end-prep, native barcode ligation, adapter ligation and clean-up, priming, and loading of the SpotON flow cell); and sequencing using the MinION platform (Oxford Nanopore Technologies Ltd., Oxford, United Kingdom).

Abbreviations

ddPCR, droplet digital PCR; gDNAs, genomic DNAs; HPTLC, high-performance thin-layer chromatography; ITS1, internal transcribed spacer 1; ITS2, internal transcribed spacer 2; LAMP, loop-mediated isothermal amplification; LMTIA, ladder-shape melting temperature isothermal amplification; PCR, polymerase chain reaction; Proofman-LMTIA, proofreading enzyme-mediated probe cleavage coupled with ladder-shape melting temperature isothermal amplification; UPLC-QTOF/MS, quadrupole time-of-flight mass spectrometry; 5.8S rRNA, 5.8S ribosomal RNA.

Results

LMTIA primers and probe design

The specific target sequence of *Hedyotis corymbosa* with a ladder-shaped melting temperature curve is shown in Fig. 1. The corresponding LMTIA primers, designed using the online software Primer3Plus (<http://www.primer3plus.com/>), are listed in Table 1. The target sequence of *H. corymbosa* was aligned with the corresponding sequences of *H. diffusa*, *H. pinifolia*, and *H. tenelliflora* using DNAMAN software. The probe was designed based on the LF primer, incorporating a 3' end mismatch nucleotide (A→G), as shown in Table 1 and Fig. 2.

DNA preparation and sample authenticity verification

Genomic DNA was extracted from samples of *H. corymbosa*, *H. diffusa*, *H. pinifolia*, and *H. tenelliflora* using the Plant Genomic DNA Nucleic Acid Extraction Kit (Xian Tianlong Technology Co., Ltd., Xi'an, Shanxi Province, China). The concentration of the gDNA, determined using a NanoDrop One spectrophotometer (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham, MA, USA), was ≥ 10 ng/ μ L with A260/A280 ratios between 1.8 and 2.0. The ITS1, 5.8S rRNA gene, and ITS2 regions were amplified using PCR (forward primer: ATGCGATACTTGGTGTGAAT; reverse primer: GACGCTTCTCCAGACTACAATT; cycling conditions: 30 cycles of 98 °C for 5 s, 54 °C for 10 s, and 72 °C for 5 s) and sequenced by General Biological Systems (Anhui) Co., Ltd. (Chuzhou, Anhui Province, China). Sequencing confirmed that the samples provided by Yuzhou Houshengtang Traditional Chinese Medicine Co., Ltd. (Xuchang, Henan Province, China) were authentic. Therefore, the extracted gDNAs were suitable as templates for temperature optimization, sensitivity determination, specificity testing, and repeatability and reliability assessment of the Proofman-LMTIA method.

Temperature optimization and specification determination

To optimize the temperature and evaluate specificity, 1 ng of *H. corymbosa* gDNA was used as the positive control, while 1 ng of *H. diffusa*, *H. pinifolia*, and *H. tenelliflora* gDNA, as well as ddH₂O, were used as negative controls. The LMTIA reaction was carried out at 60 °C, 61 °C, and 62 °C, respectively. As shown in Fig. 3, all positive controls yielded positive results, and all negative controls yielded negative results, indicating high specificity of the Proofman-LMTIA method at all tested temperatures. However, amplification efficiency was lowest at 60 °C. Therefore, 61 °C was selected as the optimal reaction temperature for subsequent experiments.

Sensitivity determination of the Proofman-LMTIA method

For sensitivity determination, 1 μ L of *H. corymbosa* gDNA at concentrations of 1 ng/ μ L, 100 pg/ μ L, and 10 pg/ μ L was added to the Proofman-LMTIA reaction system. ddH₂O was used as the negative control. As shown in Fig. 4, the established Proofman-LMTIA method was able to detect *H. corymbosa* gDNA at a minimum concentration of 10 pg, indicating high sensitivity.

Repeatability and reliability assessment of the Proofman-LMTIA method

In this experiment, 500 pg of *Hedyotis corymbosa* gDNA was used as the positive control, and ddH₂O was used as the negative control to assess the repeatability and reliability of the

Figure 1. Target sequence with ladder-shaped melting temperature curves for detection of *H. corymbosa*. Note: The ordinate represents temperature (°C); the abscissa represents the nucleic acid base sequence (nt).

Figure 2. Alignment of the target sequence of *H. corymbosa* with the corresponding sequences of *H. diffusa*, *H. pinifolia*, or *H. tenelliflora*. Note: The differential base between the target sequence of *H. corymbosa* and those of *H. diffusa*, *H. pinifolia*, or *H. tenelliflora* was T→C; thus, the 3' end mismatch nucleotide of the Proofman probe was designed as A→G.

Table 1. The sequence of LMTIA and primers and probes, as well as the target sequence.

Name	Sequence
<i>Hedyotis corymbosa</i> (L.) Lam.	F: 5'- GGGAGGCCAACTTCCGTTTTTCATCGTCGCCACCCCC-3'
	B: 5'-AGTTGGCCTCCCGTGTTTTTACGGAGGACTCGAATTTAGGC-3'
	LF: 5'- CGCGCTTCGCATTGC-3'
	LB: 5'- CTCTGGCAGCGCGG-3'
	Probe: 5'BHQ2-CGCGCTTCGCG-3'Cy5
Target of the Amplification	CATCGTCGCCACCCCTCGCAATGCGAAGCGGGGTGACGGAAGTTGGCCTCCCGTTCTCCTGGCAGCGCGCCGGCCTAAATTCGAGTCTCCGT

Figure 3. Temperature optimization and specificity determination of the Proofman-LMTIA method for detection of *H. corymbosa*. Note: **A.** Amplification plots of proofman-LMTIA reaction system at 60 °C; **B.** Amplification plots of proofman-LMTIA reaction system at 61 °C; **C.** Amplification plots of proofman-LMTIA reaction system at 62 °C.

Figure 4. Sensitivity determination of the Proofman-LMTIA method. Note: The blue amplification curve corresponds to 1 ng of gDNA extracted from the dry whole herb of *H. corymbosa*; the bright red curve represents 100 pg; and the dark red curve represents 10 pg.

Proofman-LMTIA method. As shown in Fig. 5, all positive controls exhibited nearly identical amplification curves and amplification efficiency at the reaction temperature of 61 °C, while all negative controls remained negative. These results indicate that the established Proofman-LMTIA method demonstrated satisfactory repeatability and reliability.

Commercial sample test

Eight dried whole herb samples of the traditional Chinese medicine *H. diffusa* were tested for the presence of the adulterant *H. corymbosa* using the established Proofman-LMTIA method and third-generation sequencing. As shown in Fig. 6, six samples contained *H. corymbosa* components. The results were consistent with those obtained from third-generation sequencing, indicating that three-fourths of the traditional Chinese medicine samples were adulterated with *H. corymbosa*.

Discussion

There has been growing research interest in the identification of Chinese medicinal herbs (Luo et al. 2024), and many advanced techniques have been introduced for this application, including LAMP (Rodrigues et al. 2024), ddPCR (Xu et al. 2022; Xu et al. 2025), DNA metabarcoding (Bansala et al. 2018; Raclariu et al. 2018; Xin et al. 2018; Noh et al. 2021), HPTLC (Raclariu et al. 2018), infrared spectroscopy (An et al. 2024; Luo et al. 2024), UPLC-QTOF/MS (Jin et al. 2024), and LMTIA (Zhang et al. 2023; Liu et al. 2024; Cui et al. 2024a). Among these, the LMTIA technique has shown high potential due to its

unique features: rapidity, sensitivity, specificity, repeatability, ease of operation, and cost-effectiveness (Wang et al. 2021). The current study, which established the Proofman-LMTIA method for the detection of *H. corymbosa*, further demonstrates the robustness, stability, and practical value of the LMTIA technique.

Compared with the previous study (Zhang et al. 2023; Liu et al. 2024; Cui et al. 2024a, 2024b), the procedure for developing the Proofman-LMTIA method was improved in this study. Specifically, temperature optimization and specificity determination were integrated into a single experiment, avoiding potential issues where the LMTIA reaction might show low specificity at the selected optimal temperature.

The sensitivity of the established Proofman-LMTIA method for the detection of *H. corymbosa* was 10 pg of gDNA, which is consistent with previously reported Proofman-LMTIA methods for the rapid discrimination of *Panax quinquefolium* and *P. ginseng* (Zhang et al. 2023), the detection of *Bupleurum scorzonifolium* Willd. and *B. chinense* DC (Liu et al. 2024), and the identification of *Radix Achyranthis Bidentatae* and *Radix Cyathulae* (Cui et al. 2024a). These findings further verify that the LMTIA technique is both sensitive and robust, making it a suitable approach for the rapid authentication of traditional Chinese herbs.

Furthermore, the practicality and accuracy of the established Proofman-LMTIA method were validated by third-generation sequencing during the commercial sample test. However, every method has its limitations. At present, the LMTIA technique cannot be used for quantitative analysis. Therefore, future efforts should aim to enhance the technique to enable both qualitative and quantitative detection.

Figure 5. Repeatability and reliability assessment of the Proofman-LMTIA method. Note: The eight red amplification curves represent positive reactions using 500 pg of gDNA extracted from the dry whole herb of *H. corymbosa*.

Figure 6. Detection of *H. corymbosa* in traditional Chinese medicine *H. diffusa* samples using the Proofman-LMTIA method. Note: PC: Positive Control (1 ng gDNAs extracted from the dry whole herb of *H. corymbosa*); NC: Negative Control (ddH₂O); 1: sample 1; 2: sample 2; 3: sample 3; 4: sample 4; 5: sample 5; 6: sample 6; 7: sample 7; 8: sample 8.

Conclusion

The Proofman-LMTIA method for detecting *Hedyotis corymbosa* in the traditional Chinese medicine *H. diffusa* was successfully established in this study. The optimal reaction temperature was 61 °C. The method specifically amplified the gDNA of *H. corymbosa* without cross-reactivity to *H. diffusa*, *H. pinifolia*, or *H. tenelliflora*. The sensitivity of the assay was 10 pg of gDNA extracted from dried whole herbs of *H. corymbosa*, and the LMTIA amplification was completed within 20 min. This study provides a useful reference for the identification of authentic and adulterated traditional Chinese medicines.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Use of AI

No use of AI was reported.

Funding

This study was supported by the National University Student Innovation and Entrepreneurship Training Program (202410480038), the Technology Project of Henan Province (Grant No. 242102321128), the Natural Science Foundation of China (Grant No. 32172300), the Central Government Guides the Local Science and Technology Development Special Fund (Nos: Z20231811102)

References

- An Y, Li Y, Wei W, Li Z, Zhang J, Yao C, Li J, Bi Q, Qu H, Pan H (2024) Species discrimination of multiple botanical origins of *Fritillaria* species based on infrared spectroscopy, thin layer chromatography-image analysis and untargeted metabolomics. *Phytomedicine* 123: 155228. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.phymed.2023.155228>
- Bansala S, Thakur S, Mangal M, Mangal AK, Gupta RK (2018) DNA barcoding for specific and sensitive detection of *Cuminum cuminum* adulteration in *Bunium persicum*. *Phytomedicine* 50: 178–183. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.phymed.2018.04.023>
- Cui P, Hu Z, Guo M, Wang Y, Xu D, Yao W, Liu J, Song C, Sun J, Xiao F, Wang D (2024) Rapid and duplex detection of sweetpotato and maize components in starch products using Proofman-LMTIA method. *Microchemical Journal* 204: 111082. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.microc.2024.111082>
- Cui P, Yang L, Hu Z, Yao W, Liu J, Song C, Sun J, Xiao Fg, Yin B, Wang D (2024) Rapid identification of *Radix Achyranthis Bidentatae* and *Radix Cyathulae* ingredients using Proofman-LMTIA method. *Journal of Food Composition and Analysis* 136: 106806. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jfca.2024.106806>
- Huang F, Pang J, Xu L, Niu W, Zhang Y, Li S, Li X (2022) *Hedyotis diffusa* injection induces ferroptosis via the Bax/Bcl2/VDAC2/3 axis in lung adenocarcinoma. *Phytomedicine* 104: 154319. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.phymed.2022.154319>
- Jin T, Liu F, Jiang Y, Wang L, Lu X, Li P, Li H (2021) Molecular-networking-guided discovery of species-specific markers for discriminating five medicinal *Paris* herbs. *Phytomedicine*. 85: 153542. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.phymed.2021.153542>
- Li M, Jiang RW, Hon PM, Cheng L, Li LL, Zhou JR, Shaw PC (2010) Authentication of the anti-tumor herb *Baihuasheshicao* with bioactive marker compounds and molecular sequences. *Food Chemistry* 119(3): 1239–1245. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodchem.2009.09.013>
- Liang Z, He M, Fong W, Jiang Z, Zhao Z (2008) A comparable, chemical and pharmacological analysis of the traditional Chinese medicinal herbs *Oldenlandia diffusa* and *O. corymbosa* and a new valuation of their biological potential. *Phytomedicine* 15: 259–267. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.phymed.2008.01.003>
- Liu J, Wang Y, Li T, Huang K, Song C, Cui P, et al. (2024) Dual detection of *Bupleurum scorzonerifolium* Willd. and *Bupleurum chinense* DC. using proofman-LMTIA method. *Chemical and Biological Technologies in Agriculture* 11: 104. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40538-024-00637-2>
- as well as Henan Province University Science and Technology Innovation Talent Project (Grant No. 23HASTIT048).
- ### Author contributions
- D.W. and Y.W. designed the research study. Y.W. and J.T. performed the research. D.Z. analyzed the data. Y.W. designed the primers and probes. B.Y. provided the resources. D.W. and Y.W. wrote the manuscript. All authors read and approved the manuscript.
- ### Author ORCIDs
- Deguo Wang <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0594-9533>
- ### Data availability
- The data used to support this study's findings are available from the corresponding author upon request.
- Luo Y, Yang H, Tao G (2024) Systematic review on fingerprinting development to determine adulteration of Chinese herbal medicines. *Phytomedicine* 129: 155667. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.phymed.2024.155667>
- Noh P, Kim WJ, Yang S, Choi G, Moon BC (2021) PCR-based rapid diagnostic tools for the authentication of medicinal mistletoe species. *Phytomedicine* 91: 153667. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.phymed.2021.153667>
- Raclariu AC, Țebrencu CE, Ichim MC, Ciupercă OT, Brysting AK, De Boer H (2018) What's in the box? Authentication of *Echinacea* herbal products using DNA metabarcoding and HPTLC. *Phytomedicine* 44: 32–38. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.phymed.2018.03.058>
- Rodrigues V, Honrado M, Santos J, Pinto MA, Amaral JS (2024) Development of a loop-mediated isothermal amplification assay for the rapid detection of *Styphnolobium japonicum* (L.) Schott as an adulterant of *Ginkgo biloba* (L.). *Phytomedicine* 128: 155322. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.phymed.2023.155322>
- Wang D, Wang Y, Zhang M, Zhang Y, Sun J, Song C, Xiao F, Ping Y, Pan C, Hu Yn, Wang C, Liu Y (2021) Ladder-shape melting temperature isothermal amplification of nucleic acids. *BioTechniques* 71(1): 359–370. <https://doi.org/10.2144/btn-2020-0173>
- Xiao F, Zhang Y, Gu M, Xi X, Zhang Y, Sun J, Wei Q, Hu B, Zhang G, Wang D (2024) Comparative study on the target sequences of thaumatin-like Protein (TLP) and internal transcribed spacer (ITS) in the detection of corn component in edible oil by ladder-shape melting temperature isothermal amplification (LMTIA). *LWT-Food Science and Technology* 197: 115903. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lwt.2024.115903>
- Xin T, Su C, Lin Y, Wang S Xu Z, Song J (2018) Precise species detection of traditional Chinese patent medicine by shotgun metagenomic sequencing. *Phytomedicine* 47: 40–47. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.phymed.2018.04.048>
- Xu K, Zhang Z, Wang Y, Cheng X, Jin H, Wei F, Ma S (2025) MGB probe-based multiplex droplet digital PCR for the interspecific identification of *Notopterygii Rhizoma et Radix* in herbal materials and preparations. *Phytomedicine* 136: 156325. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.phymed.2024.156325>
- Xu W, Zhu P, Xin T, Lou Q, Li R, Fu W, Ma T, Song J (2022) Droplet digital PCR for the identification of plant-derived adulterants in highly processed products. *Phytomedicine* 105: 154376. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.phymed.2022.154376>

- Yao Wei, Wang Y, Zhou D, Liu J, Song C, Zhang X, Wang D, Wang Y (2025) Comparison of Different Plant Genomic DNA Extraction Kits Based on Proofman-LMTIA Technology. *Phytochemical Analysis* 36(4): 1118–1129. <https://doi.org/10.1002/pca.3497>
- Yu J, Li M, Guo X, Wang R, Chiu SW, Shaw PC, But PPH (2012) Value of FINS depends on choice of DNA locus as shown in Baihuasheshecao. *Journal of Food and Drug Analysis* 20(4): 879–886. <https://doi.org/10.6227/jfda.2012200418>
- Zhang J, Huo J, Zhao Z, Lu Y, Hong Z, Li H, Chen D (2022) An anticomplement homogeneous polysaccharide from *Hedyotis diffusa* attenuates lipopolysaccharide-induced acute lung injury and inhibits neutrophil extracellular trap formation. *Phytomedicine* 107: 154453. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.phymed.2022.154453>
- Zhang X, Li Z, Zhang Y, Xu D, Zhang L, Xiao F, Wang D (2023) Rapid Discrimination of *Panax quinquefolium* and *Panax ginseng* Using the Proofman-Duplex-LMTIA Technique. *Molecules* 28: 6872. <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules28196872>
- Zou W, Dong Y, Yang S, Gong L, Liu M (2021) *Imperatae rhizoma-Hedyotis diffusa* Willd. herbal pair alleviates nephrotic syndrome by integrating anti-inflammatory and hypolipidaemic effects. *Phytomedicine* 90: 153644. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.phymed.2021.153644>